

A second British record of *Paragus quadrifasciatus* Meigen (Diptera, Syrphidae)

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Summary

We report the second UK record and the first specimen for *Paragus quadrifasciatus* Meigen, 1822, found in Stratford, London. We provide an introduction to the species and discuss the context around the finding.

Paragus quadrifasciatus Meigen, 1822 is a small, widely distributed fly found in Europe (Goeldlin de Tiefenau 1974) and across Asia (Gao 1991; Jabbari *et al.* 2018; Thompson and Ghorpadé 1988). In Europe, it has typically been found in the south and along the Mediterranean, though in recent years its range has extended northwards, and the species is now firmly established in areas of Belgium and the Netherlands, particularly in association with railway lines (Hoverfly Recording Scheme 2025). Despite recent research showing that some hoverfly species migrate over hundreds of kilometres of open ocean (Doyle *et al.* 2025) and despite its multi-continental range, the first *P. quadrifasciatus* record in the United Kingdom was in 2023 from Cheriton, Kent, near the terminal of the Channel Tunnel. No further individuals had been found there on subsequent visits to the site or identified anywhere else.

In July 2025, during a rooftop-garden pollinator survey in the Queen Elizabeth Olympic Park (QEOP), Stratford, we caught a hoverfly we could not immediately classify, and stored it in ethanol for subsequent identification.

Fig. 1. *Paragus quadrifasciatus* specimen caught in the Queen Elizabeth Olympic Park as seen through a dissection microscope: (a) whole individual; (b) close-up showing distinctive parallel grey ‘dusting’ stripes on thorax, yellow tipped scutellum, and yellow markings on tergites two and three of abdomen; (c) close-up showing distinct bands of white hairs on the eyes.

Using Stubbs and Falk (2002), we thought it was likely a member of the genus *Paragus*, but were unable to identify it to species level. Through a combination of online resources and

image trawling we subsequently tentatively identified the specimen (Fig. 1) as a male of *P. quadrifasciatus*. This was later confirmed by Roger Morris and Duncan and Olga Sivell, and through further species descriptors in Bot and Van de Meutter (2023) and Speight (2024). To our knowledge, this is the first specimen and only the second record of *P. quadrifasciatus* in Britain.

The rooftop-garden in which we found the individual is part of UCL East's QEOP campus, and was explicitly designed as a 'living lab'. Despite only measuring ~30m x 7m, the garden has high wildflower species richness, including purpletop vervain (*Verbena bonariensis*), purple loosestrife (*Lythrum salicaria*) and meadow crane's-bill (*Geranium pratense*). We caught the individual on a large artichoke thistle flower (*Cynara cardunculus*) which had an aphid infestation: *P. quadrifasciatus* is known to forage around the Cardueae (thistle) tribe, with males behaving territorially (Hoverfly Recording Scheme 2025), and females laying their eggs amongst aphid populations for the larvae to feed on (Gao *et al.* 1996; Krsteska 2010). Furthermore, Passaseo *et al.* (2020) demonstrated that urban green roofs in Geneva can support local populations of the species, which is otherwise rare in Switzerland.

UCL East in Stratford is very close to the High Speed 1 railway line which runs through Stratford International and onwards to the Channel Tunnel. The prior UK sighting (Warry *et al.* 2024) was outside the channel tunnel terminus and, given the tendency of Belgian populations to associate with railways, it seems plausible that the species may have been introduced along the railway. Alternatively, transported foodstuffs also enter London from this direction by road. Given that neither the Eurostar nor any other international trains have ever stopped at Stratford, and that the nearest in-use international station is London St Pancras (5 miles away), we find it unlikely that this individual is a solitary vagrant. However, we failed to see another *P. quadrifasciatus* individual over the course of a week of intensive surveying, decreasing the likelihood of there being an established local population. As males can be territorial, it is possible that its presence put off other males from foraging in that area; but given that we caught it on the first of five days' intensive sampling we would expect other males in the area to take over the location during the duration of the survey. This investigation was part of a wider study of trialling the use of molecular methods to detect pollinators otherwise unseen during traditional surveys. We are currently in the DNA extraction and sequencing phase of the study, and it remains to be seen whether we can detect *P. quadrifasciatus* DNA. As we caught the individual on the first of five days, were we to detect molecular evidence of its presence towards the end of the sampling period it would be possible that there is indeed an established local population: we look forward to reporting the results.

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